

Influence of Palm Bunch Ash (PBA) in the Treatment of Erosion-Prone Soils: A Review

Onyechere, I. C.^{1*}, Ogbulie, J. N.², Uche, C. C.³, Onyechere, A. U.⁴

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Federal University of Technology Owerri,

²Department of Sustainable Social Development, Center of Excellence in Sustainable Procurement, Environmental and Social Standard, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Nigeria.

³Department of Environmental Management, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Soil Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo.

*Corresponding author: onyechere.chigozie@futo.edu.ng

Received: November 30, 2025; Accepted: December 26, 2025; Published: January 29, 2026

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18412632>

Abstract: In tropical regions of the world such as Nigeria, soil erosion poses a major environmental and engineering challenge due to high rainfall intensity and poor soil structure which encourage land degradation. It has been customary practice to use ordinary Portland cement to stabilize soil erosion-prone soils. However, the environmental and health hazards and excessive cost associated with ordinary Portland cement has attracted the attention of researchers to seek sustainable, low-cost and environmentally friendly soil improvement materials such as agricultural waste ashes like Palm Bunch Ash (PBA). PBA, which is obtained by burning empty oil-palm fruit bunches to ash, has acquired an overwhelming interest as an affordable, eco-friendly and sustainable material for soil stabilization in erosion-prone soils of tropical regions. PBA has a high pozzolanic capacity due to the fact that it is very rich in oxides of Potassium, Calcium, Silica, and Magnesium thus, presenting it as a suitable material for stabilizing weak or erosion-prone soils. This work presents a critical review on the effects of PBA on the geotechnical and physicochemical characteristics of soils, mechanisms by which PBA affects soil characteristics and the behaviour of soil when it is subjected to structural load. The paper detects mixing ratios of PBA to soil mass that will yield best performance in enhancing soil properties, identifies the economic and environment advantages of using PBA in soil stabilization and examines the challenges experienced in the practical use of PBA in treating erosion-prone soils and in general eco-friendly and sustainable geotechnical engineering.

Keywords: *Eco-Friendly, Soil Erosion, Palm Bunch Ash, Agricultural Waste, Soil Stabilization.*

1. Introduction

Soil erosion is a major threat to agricultural productivity, infrastructure stability, and environmental sustainability, particularly in tropical regions like Nigeria (Ankrah et al., 2023; Genchi et al., 2025). It causes reduction of land area available for agriculture, depletion of soil nutrients, collapse of buildings and other civil infrastructures and destruction of natural ecosystems (Obianyo et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2018). Soil erosion is a significant environmental and geotechnical challenge in many parts of Nigeria, including the southeastern Nigeria (Medeiros et al., 2025). Tropical climates, characterized by intense rainfall, combined with deforestation, poor drainage, and lateritic soil composition, contributes to severe soil degradation and gully formation (Li et al., 2025). In Southeastern Nigeria, the menace of soil erosion is further aggravated by anthropogenic activities like; deforestation, over utilization of farmlands, construction of more buildings and paved roads and indiscriminate sand mining among others (Ajayi et al., 2024). These conditions compromise the structural integrity of buildings, roads, and other infrastructure within the region. Conventional soil stabilization methods make use of cement or

lime as a soil stabilization agent (Onyechere et al., 2025), (Eziefula et al., 2025). However, the environmental and health hazards and excessive cost associated with ordinary Portland cement has attracted the attention of researchers to seek sustainable, low-cost and environmentally friendly soil improvement materials such as agricultural waste ashes like Palm Bunch Ash (Alshawmar, 2024).

The increase in human population, especially in the developing countries of the world, increase in developmental projects, increase in the rate of consumption of goods among other factors have caused escalating increase in the generation of waste in the society. This calls for concern and deliberate search for means of converting some of these wastes to wealth to encourage sustainable waste management (Ajayi et al., 2024). Engineers have found some agricultural wastes like; Palm bunch ash, Coconut Shell ash, Bamboo leave ash, Groundnut shell ash, Sawdust ash and Rice husk ash useful in the production of concrete and in soil stabilization due to their high content of oxides of Calcium, Aluminum, Silicon and Potassium (Onyechere, 2022). Palm Bunch Ash (PBA), a byproduct of palm oil processing, is rich in silica,

potassium, calcium, and other oxides, making it a promising material for soil stabilization. In addition, palm bunch is in abundance in most areas within the Southern part of Nigeria and the entire South-Eastern Nigeria (Kumarasinghe, 2021). PBA contains oxides of CaO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and K₂O, which can react with soil minerals to form cementitious compounds, improving soil strength, cohesion, and resistance to erosion. Previous studies have shown that palm bunch ash can improve soil strength, reduce plasticity, and increase bearing capacity, making it suitable for geotechnical applications.

Oke & Osinubi (2019) Used PBA to stabilize lateritic soil and observed that 8% of PBA by mass of the soil increases the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and the California bearing ratio (CBR) of the soil which increases the soil's resistance to erosion. (Onyelowe, 2019) made use of nanosized PBA in the stabilization of lateritic soil of Oloro, Umuahia, Nigeria and observed that addition of 9% of nanosized PBA by weight of the soil increased the CBR, UCS and maximum dry density (MDD) of the soil sample. Applying PBA to erosion-prone soils could offer an eco-friendly and cost-effective solutions to

soil stabilization, promote sustainable waste management, and reduce over reliance on conventional chemical stabilizers like cement and lime. Utilizing PBA offers a dual benefit: improving the geotechnical characteristics of erosion-prone soils and promoting agricultural waste management in an environmentally sustainable way (Tardio et al., 2018). This research aims to establish from the works of previous researchers, the effects of PBA in the treatment erosion-prone soils.

2. Origin and Composition of Palm Bunch Ash (PBA)

Palm Bunch Ash is obtained by burning empty palm fruit bunches in a controlled manner. These empty palm fruit bunches are generally dumped indiscriminately around many oil palm processing centers in the rural areas. The ash is greyish to black in color and alkaline in nature. The chemical characteristics of PBA vary depending on the method of combustion adopted and the combustion temperature. From the works of Otunyo & Chukuigwe, (2018), the chemical composition of PBA (by weight) is given as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Chemical Properties of Palm Bunch Ash Constituent

Constituent	Percentage Weight of PBA (%)
MgO	0.85
Fe ₂ O ₂	0.49
CaO ₂	14.7
Al ₂ O ₃	15.38
SiO ₂	60.85
TiO ₂	0.01
Na ₂ O	0.92
ZnO	1.00
CuO	Trace
CdO	Trace
MnO	0.88
PbO	0.14
LiO	6.4

From the Table, The high aluminium and calcium contents of PBA contributes to pozzolanic activities when mixed with clayey or silty soils. The pozzolanic activity of PBA depends on burning temperature, fineness, and replacement proportion. According to the works of Waluyo et al. (2023), the major oxides contained in PBA include;

(a) Silica (SiO₂): This is often the dominant oxide and makes PBA interesting as a supplementary (pozzolanic) material, but the amount of amorphous (reactive) silica depends strongly on burning temperature and cooling: uncontrolled open burning often yields crystalline silica (less reactive), while controlled combustion and post-treatment (washing, acid extraction or heat control) increases reactive silica content.

(b) Potassium (K₂O): This can be very high in some palm ashes (which is why ashes are used as potash fertilizers). However, Very high K content reduces suitability as a cementitious pozzolan unless processed/washed.

(c) Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃: These are usually minor compared with SiO₂ but still reported; CaO and MgO vary with contamination (soil, shells) and burner conditions.

In the works of Eziefula et al., (2025), the PBA was produced by burning empty palm bunches in a furnace at a temperature of about 650°C in open air. In their work, the chemical analysis of PBA was done using energy dispersive X-ray analysis and obtained the result given in Table 2.

Table 2: Chemical Composition of PBA

Oxide	%PBA by mass
SiO ₂	44.217
CaO	30.514
K ₂ O	4.565
Al ₂ O ₃	3.610
MgO	3.388
P ₂ O ₅	2.701
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.313
Na ₂ O	1.286
MnO	0.788
ZnO	0.635
BaO	0.168
TiO ₂	0.131
SO ₃	1.970
LOI	2.714

Note: LOI represents Loss on Ignition.

3. Mechanisms of Soil Improvement with PBA

The influence of PBA on the properties of soil properties is as a result of several physical and chemical mechanisms:

(a) Cation Exchange and Flocculation:

The exchange of cations such calcium and potassium found in PBA with monovalent ions like (Na^+ , H^+) in soil minerals reduces double-layer thickness, promoting particle aggregation and increased shear strength of soil.

(b) Pozzolanic Reactions:

Reactive Silicon oxide (SiO_2) and Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) present in PBA reacts with calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) in the soil in the presence of water to form cementitious compounds (calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) and calcium aluminate hydrate (C–A–H)), which bind soil particles together, forming very strong inter-particle bond which increases cohesion and enhances soil shear strength and stability.

(c) Reduction in Plasticity and Swelling:

PBA addition in soil reduces the plasticity index and swelling potential of expansive soils, thereby enhancing stability under varying moisture conditions (Onyelowe, 2019).

d) Increase in Cohesion and Bearing Capacity:

The particles of PBA forms fillers in the PBA-Soil mixture which fills the voids in between the soil grains, hence reducing the pore spaces, increases particle interlock. This increases soil density and reduces soil permeability. Stabilized soils exhibit improved unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) and increases the bearing capacity of the soil which are essential in resisting soil erosion and road subgrade performance (Rahmat et al., 2021).

4. Influence of PBA on Geotechnical Properties of Soils

Results of many research studies have shown significant improvements in the geotechnical properties of soil when treated with PBA. PBA being an agro-waste pozzolan rich in SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and CaO improves geotechnical parameters like; CBR, UCS, Shear strength of soil when mixed with soil. It also modifies compaction and consistency parameters when mixed with soil (Otunyo & Chukuigwe, 2018).

(a) Compaction Characteristics (MDD & OMC)

Many studies report decreased maximum dry density (MDD) and increased optimum moisture content (OMC) with increasing PBA content (because PBA has lower particle density and higher water affinity). This influences field compaction specifications and necessitates revised compaction control when using PBA (Onyechere et al., 2025). In the works of Otunyo & Chukuigwe, (2018), MDD and OMC increase as PBA content increases up to an optimum content of 20 – 25% and then decreases at higher PBA content. This is because, the particles of PBA forms fillers in the PBA-Soil mixture which fills the voids in between the soil grains, hence reducing the pore spaces, increases particle interlock and increases the density of the soil. Beyond the optimum content, the excess ash being porous in nature creates more voids which reduces the density of the soil (Otunyo & Chukuigwe, 2018).

(b) Strength - Unconfined compressive strength (UCS)

UCS typically increases with PBA addition up to an optimum content; the gains are larger when PBA is activated by lime or cement or when PBA is nanosized. Reported

optimum UCS improvements vary: e.g., several studies reported substantial UCS gains for lateritic soils with PBA contents in the range **3–20%** (by dry weight) depending on soil type, curing and whether lime/cement was present (Onyelowe, 2019). The strength gain is as a result of the pozzolanic effect of PBA with soil due to its high content of Silicon and Aluminum oxides, also PBA particles are mainly fine and acts as filler materials which fill the pore spaces of soil mass, increasing the density and strength of soil.

(c) Bearing capacity - California Bearing Ratio (CBR)

Unsoaked and soaked CBR values often increase markedly when laterite/clay is stabilized with PBA, with reported optimum contents varying widely (e.g., 6–15% or higher depending on whether PBA is used alone or blended with cementitious activators). Several works indicate PBA can produce CBR values suitable for low-volume pavement subgrades when optimized (Otunyo & Chukuigwe, 2018).

(d) Shear strength (cohesion and friction angle)

Chemical stabilization (PBA + cement/lime) tends to raise cohesion and may also

increase internal friction angle via particle bonding and improved gradation. Reported increases in cohesion are sometimes large (some studies report near-doubling at certain mixes), especially at combinations such as 20% PBA + moderate cement content — although specific numbers vary with soil and testing method (Waluyo et al., 2023). This is because, the reactive Silicon oxide (SiO_2) and Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) present in PBA reacts with calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) in the soil in the presence of water to form cementitious compounds (calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) and calcium aluminate hydrate (C–A–H)), which bind soil particles together, forming very strong inter-particle bond which increases cohesion and enhances soil shear strength and stability (Onyechere et al., 2025).

(e) Permeability and erodibility

Laboratory tests indicate PBA reduces permeability (through void filling and C–S–H formation), and treated specimens show lower mass loss under simulated erosion tests. However, controlled comparative erodibility (flume) data remain limited and are an important area for additional research (Waluyo et al., 2023).

These improvements indicate the dual benefits of using PBA: improvement of soil strength and reduction of erodibility.

5. PBA Applications in Erosion Control

PBA is applied in the treatment of erosion-prone soils due to its ability to improve soil properties. It has been applied in the following ways;

(a) Stabilization of Soils prone to Gully Erosion

PBA when properly mixed in the right proportion with clayey or sandy soils, it the shear strength and density of the soil, it also leads to reduction in soil permeability, thus increasing the erodibility resistance of the soil. It also makes the soil less permeable, thus resisting surface runoff (Ajayi et al., 2024).

(b) Stabilization of Subgrade and Embankment

PBA when properly mixed in the right proportion with soil, increases the maximum dry density of soil and its shear strength, thus leading to increase in the bearing capacity of the soil and reduces soil erosion.

(c) Eco-friendly Soil Treatment

Using PBA in treating erosion-prone soils encourages utilization of agricultural waste instead of industrial stabilizers like ordinary Portland cement which is very expensive and has several environmental and health hazards, supporting environmental sustainability (Almuaythir et al., 2024).

The percentage of PBA for optimum performance and effective stabilization ranges between 4–10% by weight of soil, depending on soil type and desired performance.

6. Environmental and Economic Considerations

- (a) **Sustainability:** PBA is a renewable waste product with minimal environmental impact compared to cement and lime.
- (b) **Cost Efficiency:** Local availability reduces construction costs in rural erosion-prone areas.
- (c) **Waste Management:** Promotes recycling of agricultural residues that otherwise contribute to pollution.

However, uncontrolled burning and inconsistent ash composition can limit standardization. Therefore, pre-treatment

and controlled incinerations are necessary for consistent quality.

7. Challenges and Research Gaps

Despite its promise, several challenges remain:

- Lack of standardized guidelines for PBA processing and application in geotechnical engineering.
- Limited long-term durability studies under cyclic wetting and drying conditions.
- Insufficient data on field-scale erosion control using PBA-treated soils.
- Potential leaching of soluble salts (especially K_2O) that may affect vegetation or groundwater quality.

Future research should focus on optimizing mix design, understanding the kinetics of pozzolanic reactions, and evaluating field performance under real climatic conditions.

8. Conclusion

Palm Bunch Ash offers a viable, sustainable, and low-cost means of treating erosion-prone soils. Its rich pozzolanic content enhances soil strength and density, reduces soil permeability, and improves resistance to erosion processes. Use of PBA in soil stabilization aligns with green engineering

and circular economy principles. Adopting PBA as a soil stabilizer encourages sustainable waste management, reduction in carbon emission occasioned by continuous use of Ordinary Portland Cement and supports sustainable use of natural resources. For effective utilization, standardization of burning conditions, particle fineness, and dosage optimization are required. Further field validation studies are recommended to fully integrate PBA into sustainable erosion control and soil stabilization practices.

References

- Ajayi, V., Epelle, P., & Akinwumi, I. (2024). Sustainable Soil Stabilization of Road Pavement Layers Using Waste Materials: A Mini-Review. *Detritus*, 29, 120–134. <https://doi.org/10.31025/2611-4135/2024.19434>
- Almuaythir, S., Zaini, M. S. I., Hasan, M., & Hoque, Md. I. (2024). Sustainable soil stabilization using industrial waste ash: Enhancing expansive clay properties. *Heliyon*, 10(20), e39124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e39124>
- Alshawmar, F. (2024). Utilization of Nano Silica and Plantain Leaf Ash for Improving Strength Properties of Expansive Soil. *Sustainability*, 16(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16052157>
- Ankrah, J., Monteiro, A., & Madureira, H. (2023). Shoreline Change and Coastal Erosion in West Africa: A Systematic Review of Research Progress and Policy Recommendation. *Geosciences*, 13(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences13020059>
- Eziefula, U. G., Nwosu, O. U., Udoha, C. L., Ibearugbulem, O. M., & Onyechere, I. C. (2025). Strength properties of concrete containing palm bunch ash–calcined anthill clay. *International Review of Applied Sciences and Engineering*, 16(2), 265–274. <https://doi.org/10.1556/1848.2024.00905>
- Genchi, S. A., Vitale, A. J., & Perillo, G. M. E. (2025). Coastal cliff erosion: A bibliometric analysis and literature review. *Anthropocene Coasts*, 8(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44218-025-00072-2>
- Kumarasinghe, U. (2021). A review on new technologies in soil erosion management. *Journal of Research*

- Technology and Engineering*, 2(1), 120–127.
- Li, J., Liu, S., Yang, D., Suo, F., Yu, Y., Wang, Z., & Liao, Q. (2025). The Impact of Land Use Types on the Soil Erosion Resistance in the Arid Valley Region of Southwest China. *Agriculture*, 15(4), 386. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture15040386>
- Medeiros, B. M., Cândido, B., Jimenez, P. A. J., Avanzi, J. C., & Silva, M. L. N. (2025). UAV-Based Soil Water Erosion Monitoring: Current Status and Trends. *Drones*, 9(4), 305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones9040305>
- Obianyo, I., Aboubakar Mahamat, A., Anosike-Francis, E., Stanislas, T., Geng, Y., Onyelowe, K., Odusanya, S., Onwualu, P., & Soboyejo, W. (2021). Performance of lateritic soil stabilized with combination of bone and palm bunch ash for sustainable building applications. *Cogent Engineering*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2021.1921673>
- Oke, J. A., & Osinubi, K. J. (2019). Oil palm empty fruit bunch ash as a sustainable stabilizer for laterite sub-base of highway pavements. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 640, 012086. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/640/1/012086>
- Onyechere, I. C. (2022). Properties of Sawdust Concrete. *Journal of Building Material Science*, 4(2), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.30564/jbms.v4i2.4818>
- Onyechere, I. C., Anya, C. U., Onodagu, P. D., Onyechere, A. U., Eziefula, U. G., Njoku, F. C., & Anyaogu, L. (2025). Influence of Rice Husk Ash on the Engineering Properties of Soil. *NIPES Journal of Science and Technology Research*, 7(2), 253–262. <https://doi.org/10.37933/nipes/7.2.2025.17>
- Onyelowe, K. C. (2019). Nanosized palm bunch ash (NPBA) stabilisation of lateritic soil for construction purposes. *International Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 13(1), 83–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19386362.2017.1322797>
- Otunyo, A. W., & Chukuigwe, C. C. (2018). Investigation of the impact of palm bunch ash on the stabilization of

- poor lateritic soil. *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, 37(3), 600.
<https://doi.org/10.4314/njt.v37i3.6>
- Rahmat, F., Fen, Y. W., Anuar, M. F., Omar, N. A. S., Zaid, M. H. M., Matori, K. A., & Khaidir, R. E. M. (2021). Synthesis and Characterization of ZnO-SiO₂ Composite Using Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch as a Potential Silica Source. *Molecules*, 26(4), 1061.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26041061>
- Tardio, G., Mickovski, S. B., Rauch, H. P., Fernandes, J. P., Acharya, M. S., Tardio, G., Mickovski, S. B., Rauch, H. P., Fernandes, J. P., & Acharya, M. S. (2018). The Use of Bamboo for Erosion Control and Slope Stabilization: Soil Bioengineering Works. In *Bamboo—Current and Future Prospects*. IntechOpen.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.75626>
- Waluyo, T., Anggraini, M., & Dwi Putri, L. (2023). The Shear Strength of Clay Stabilized with Palm Bunch Ash and Cement. *Civilla : Jurnal Teknik Sipil Universitas Islam Lamongan*, 8(2), 215–222.
<https://doi.org/10.30736/cvl.v8i2.1139>
- Williams, A. T., Rangel-Buitrago, N., Pranzini, E., & Anfuso, G. (2018). The management of coastal erosion. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 156, 4–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2017.03.022>